

ACTION OF D-MANNOSE IN URINARY TRACT INFECTIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6657940>

Abstract.

This paper presents the results of a review of studies aimed at describing the mechanism of the therapeutic effect of D-mannose in preventing infection of the lower urinary tract. A pathogenetic substantiation of the possibility of considering D-mannose as a specific antiadhesin, a competitive blocker of bacterial adhesion, is presented. The possibilities of using drugs based on D-mannose are considered. Key words: D-mannose, bacterial cystitis, E.coli, adhesive ability, dietary supplement.

Every year, 700,000 people worldwide die due to antibiotic resistance, say researchers from the Italian Society for Antimicrobial Therapy. Bacterial resistance to antibiotics is a global threat. The World Health Organization (WHO) calls for optimizing the use of antimicrobials by limiting their use in situations where they can be dispensed with. For this purpose, the possibility of using preparations based on D-mannose was considered. D-mannose is a monosaccharide, an isomer of glucose, highly soluble in water, and has a sweet taste. In the free form, D-mannose is present in many fruits and berries, that is, it is part of the normal human diet. Exogenous D-mannose is rapidly absorbed from the upper gastrointestinal tract. The monosaccharide is practically not metabolized in the liver and enters the circulatory system unchanged. Already after 30-60 minutes, by renal filtration, 90% of the incoming D-mannose is in the bladder. The latter fact is very important for the treatment and prevention of bacterial cystitis: after all, urine saturated with D-mannose, targeted reduces the adhesion of uropathogenic bacteria (strains of E. coli, Klebsiella, Proteus, etc.) to the urothelium of the renal pelvis, ureters, bladder and urethra.

Purpose: The aim of the study is to study the prospects for the use and mechanism of action of D-mannose in the treatment of inflammation of the lower urinary tract.

Materials and Methods: A thorough review of the literature of scientists working in this field was carried out, and conclusions were drawn based on their research.

Results: D-Mannose excreted by the kidneys can have a beneficial effect in UTIs caused by E. coli (E. coli causes up to 90% of acute cystitis) by disrupting its adhesion mechanisms and accelerating excretion from the human body.

Adhesion of E. coli to the urothelium and retention of the microorganism inside during urination occurs with the help of long, hair-like processes - fimbriae or pili.

this is one of the main virulence factors of E. coli. When the attachment ability of the bacterium is weak, there is a rapid removal of Escherichia coli from the bladder during urination. D-mannose blocks the fimbriae of E.Coli, thereby reducing the adhesive ability and helping to remove the uropathogen from the body⁵.

In Europe and Asia, dietary supplements with D-mannose are quite common, including both monopreparations with various concentrations of D-mannose and combined dietary supplements (combinations of D-mannose with probiotics, diuretic herbs, phytouroantiseptics, citrate buffers).

Conclusions: D-mannose therapy effectively reduces the symptoms of cystitis and does not show any side effects inherent in antibiotic therapy. Therefore, D-Mannose should be used to treat cystitis in patients with antibiotic allergy, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, and in pregnant women with preeclampsia.

